

Study on Rural Landscape Design Method under the Background of the Population Diversification

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Abstract : Population diversification phenomena becomes quite common in villages located in China's developed coastal area. Based on the analysis of the traditional rural society and its landscape characteristics, and in consideration of diversified landscape requirements due to the population diversification, with dual ideas of heritage and innovation, methods for rural landscape design were explored by taking Duxuao Village in Zhejiang Province of China as an example.

Keywords : rural landscape, population diversification, landscape design, urban management

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